

ELIXIR Commissioned Service - 2024-TECHNOLOGY-TRAINING PLATFORM

D4.1 - A professional guide with a step-by-step procedure to FAIRify training materials

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the process followed to create a professional guide with a step-by-step procedure to FAIRify ELIXIR training materials. This step-by-step procedure complements the FAIR Training Handbook, and other FAIR training resources created by the ELIXIR Training Platform. This procedure should help the ELIXIR community to FAIRify training materials created under the ELIXIR auspices (opposed to Node training materials).

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TtT	ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer
SPLASH	Skills, Professional development, Learning Assessment, Support and Help
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
PID	Persistent Identifier

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Background

Since 2018, when we established the FAIR Training Focus group at ELIXIR, several resources have been created by the members of the ELIXIR Training Platform and some in collaboration with the whole international community:

- The first was the landmark paper "[Ten Simple Rules to Make Training Materials FAIR](#)", published in PLOS Computational Biology in 2021 (16,243 views, cited 38 times). It sets the basis for a common understanding of the FAIR principles applied to training materials,
- It was followed by the [FAIR Training Handbook](#), which extends this basic understanding with several examples and more explanations of the FAIR principles applied to training materials,
- This was followed by a [checklist](#), which allows users to verify if the FAIRification steps have been taken,
- And then the [Training material made FAIR by design](#) course.

Despite these resources, many people still have a hard time actually FAIRifying their training materials - which steps to take in which order and which solutions to adopt for each step. For instance, which type of license to adopt, or which metadata standard to use when creating "ELIXIR" training materials.

Each ELIXIR Node or institution providing training can have its own rules/solutions for the FAIRification steps. For instance, at SIB, we have our own FAIRification steps with our solutions, which are described in [this workflow](#). These steps and solutions are not necessarily the same for an "ELIXIR" branded course. Some examples of ELIXIR-branded courses are the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer (TtT) and ELITMa. These two courses were developed by the ELIXIR community under the ELIXIR projects and are not owned by any specific Node. The ELIXIR-GOBLET TtT materials so far live in a Google folder, and are not yet fully FAIRified. A description of a common ELIXIR process was thus required to allow the FAIRification of not only the ELIXIR-GOBLET TtT materials, but also any other ELIXIR training materials.

Reaching an ELIXIR training materials FAIRification flowchart

As seen above, SIB already had defined a workflow to FAIRify training materials that can be found in the [SIB Training Cookbook](#). SIB's workflow was presented as a [poster](#) at the ELIXIR AHM in June 2025¹. We have used SIB's as a starting point to create the ELIXIR version.

We have started the ELIXIR process by inviting all members of the Training Platform attending the AHM to meet in front of SIB's poster and discuss the adaptations we would need to create the ELIXIR FAIRification flowchart, i.e. ELIXIR's version of that workflow. Subsequently, we held two other meetings online, announced to all members of the Training Platform, where we could further discuss any specific ELIXIR requirements. The notes of these discussions can be found [here](#).

We have then compiled all the suggestions received and created the [ELIXIR version](#), which is composed of a flowchart ([Figure 1](#)) drawing followed by the explanations and recommendations on the solutions for each step, which are the following:

1. Metadata

¹ <https://f1000research.com/posters/14-516>

Using metadata is important for making your materials findable and reusable. It is therefore very helpful to check whether the associated metadata is correct, in the right standard, and available. Metadata can be associated with training materials in many ways. Therefore, depending on the registries/databases you are using, you might have to make your metadata available in multiple places. More information in the [FAIR training handbook](#), including on the richness of metadata.

Typically, the standard used is determined by the registry or database you are using. However, one commonly used standard is the [Bioschemas Training Material standard](#). This standard is used by, amongst others, the [TeSS](#) registry. Another frequently used standard for metadata describing training material is the one used by [Zenodo](#).

For ELIXIR related courses to appear in TeSS, you need to annotate them with the [Training Material](#) profile from Bioschemas (more on how to annotate ELIXIR materials in the [ELIXIR Guide for Bioschemas Annotation of Training Assets](#)).

2. Attribution

Reuse is a good practice in developing training materials, and typically, it is absolutely necessary that you give credit to the original authors. You will find a comprehensive explanation of how to do this here:

- [Chapter 10 of the ELIXIR FAIR training handbook](#)
- [ELIXIR FAIR material by design course](#)

3. License

The default copyright laws apply if a license is not specified, meaning that no one can use, copy, distribute, or modify the materials. You need to add a license to allow others to use your materials.

For ELIXIR courses, we recommend using the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#). More information on licenses can be found:

- [ELIXIR FAIR training handbook](#)
- [ELIXIR FAIR material by design course](#)

4. Accessibility

In order to make materials open for re-use, it is important that potential re-users can easily access them, that they are in a format that can be re-used, and that they are persistently available. (Internal) servers and cloud instances are typically not a good option because they are often not stable in terms of permissions, availability, and persistence. Therefore, it is recommended to use GitHub linked with Zenodo, or, if you are not using GitHub, host materials on Zenodo. If Zenodo is not an option, you can also use other repositories like Figshare, or institutional repositories.

For ELIXIR courses, we recommend using [GitHub linked with Zenodo](#). As mentioned above, if GitHub is not used, materials can be hosted on Zenodo.

5. Versioning system

Using version control like git is a great way to share and collaborate on training materials. You can add your materials directly in the repository, e.g. in GitHub, and let participants interact with the materials through GitHub. It is also possible to host websites with GitHub pages, which might give a nicer interface for the course participants.

For ELIXIR courses, we recommend using GitHub. You can use the following template:

- ELIXIR GitHub [Lesson Template](#) and the [instructions](#) on how to use the template.

ELIXIR courses are typically hosted within the [ELIXIR Training GitHub organisation](#). Contact a member of the ELIXIR training team to get access to this organisation. If you name the repository, make sure it ends with -training. This way, it is clear that it is a training repository.

6. Zenodo

Zenodo is a repository that allows you to deposit your materials and assign a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to them. It is a great way to make your materials persistent and findable. Zenodo can be used to host training materials, as well as other materials like software, data, and publications.

7. Persistent identifier

A persistent identifier (PID) is a long-lasting reference to a document, file, page, or other object. It is used to ensure that the object can always be found, even if the URL changes. The most common PID is the DOI, which is used for scientific publications. For training materials, the DOI is often used, but there are other PIDs that can be used as well. PIDs are typically assigned if you register your materials in a database or registry.

For ELIXIR courses, we recommend using Zenodo, which assigns a DOI to your materials.

8. Specific materials

Training materials can consist of various types of files, including slides, datasets, notebooks, lecture videos, software, workflows, and more. All of these materials are valuable resources for both learners and trainers to reuse. However, with so many different types of materials, there are also numerous options for repositories. Here are some suggestions for sharing ELIXIR training material types:

- Slides: [Zenodo](#),
- Workflows: [WorkflowHub](#),
- Docker images: [DockerHub](#),
- Videos: [YouTube](#) or [Vimeo](#). These platforms are very good for sharing and viewing videos, but they are not for long-term storage. For archiving, you can use Zenodo.
- Datasets: usually it is recommended that you use the repositories that fit your datasets. For instance, ENA for genomics sequencing, PRIDE for proteomics data, etc. If you are not sure of the best repository for your datasets, you can look for the best options in [Re3data.org](#) or [FAIRsharing.org](#).

9. Glittr.org

Materials that are hosted on GitHub are often hard to find, especially if they are not indexed elsewhere. Glittr.org is a platform that indexes GitHub repositories and makes them findable. It also provides additional metadata based on the metadata available in the GitHub repository.

All ELIXIR courses on GitHub should be available from Glittr.org. If your course material is missing, submit it at <https://glittr.org/contribute>.

10. TeSS

[TeSS](#) indexes training materials and events from various sources, including GitHub repositories. It is a great platform to make your materials findable. TeSS uses the Bioschemas profile that can be automatically scraped from websites. An alternative to using Bioschemas is to manually add metadata to TeSS.

ELIXIR training materials should be findable in TeSS. Contact a member of the [TeSS team](#) to have more information on how to do these steps. But if you already annotated your materials with the Bioschemas metadata, it should be fairly easy.

11. Communication

Although now your materials have been made FAIR, it is important to communicate this to the world. You can do this by sharing your materials on social media, in newsletters, or by presenting them at conferences.

The recommended channels for sharing your training materials are the ELIXIR Weekly Brief, the ELIXIR LinkedIn pages, and any other social media that you might be using at your own institution (the more you communicate about your materials, the merrier). Contact the ELIXIR Hub [communications team](#) if you need support with ELIXIR dissemination.

Hosting of the ELIXIR FAIRification flowchart

This ELIXIR FAIRification flowchart is hosted in GitHub under the [ELIXIR Training organisation](#). Below is a screenshot of the flowchart (this image can also be found in the GitHub repo [here](#)).

Figure 1: ELIXIR FAIR training materials flowchart

The GitHub repo and all its components are “living documents.” They are available to all ELIXIR Training Platform members and the wider community, and anyone can suggest modifications and new ideas for improvement. This collaborative work is how we “walk the walk,” as it is a core part of the FAIRification steps proposed by the ELIXIR FAIR training materials standard.

Outcomes and expected impact

This procedure should now help the ELIXIR community to FAIRify training materials created under the ELIXIR auspices - any kind of ELIXIR training material created under the ELIXIR brand (opposed to Node training materials, which may have their own specifications). This flowchart is also available to any ELIXIR Node or institution to fork and adapt to their own specific needs. This should further facilitate the adoption of FAIR training materials by the ELIXIR Nodes and any worldwide institutions.

Dissemination Plans

The ELIXIR training material FAIRification flowchart is currently located in GitHub under the [ELIXIR Training organisation](#). To increase its dissemination and usage, we will also link it in the FAIR Handbook and in [SPLASH](#) as well, and communicate within ELIXIR and social networks, increasing its reach and visibility.